

THE VIOLENCE IN FAMILY AS TRADITION AND HABIT: SOME HISTORICAL ASPECTS

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VIOLENȚA ÎN FAMILIE CA TRADIȚIE ȘI OBICEI: PERSPECTIVĂ ISTORICĂ

Rezumat. În articol sunt prezentate aspecte istorice ale fenomenului de violență în familie și este argumentată necesitatea studierii acestui fenomen în Sectorul Arab din Israel din perspectiva „the exchange/social theory”, elaborată de cercetătorul american Richard J. Gelles. Conceptul de violență în familie nu este clar definit până în prezent, pentru că este un proces complex și multidimensional.

Fenomenul în sine este necesar de a fi cercetat din perspectiva unui model general cu o bază vastă de cunoaștere a fiecărui tip de violență. F.I. Nye a realizat extensia științifică a „the exchange/social theory” prin explicarea violenței în familie prin controlul social extern și intern. Considerăm această extensie a fi cea mai potrivită pentru a cerceta fenomenul de violență în familiile din sectorul arab al Israelului.

Cuvinte-cheie: violență, relații, familie, conflicte, soție, soț, copii, prieteni, colegi, școală.

Abstract. The article gives historical aspects of phenomenon of family violence and gives an explanation of scientific need to research this phenomenon in Arab Sector of Israel from Richard J. Gelles's the exchange/social theory. The concept of family violence has unclear configuration. Family violence is considered to be a very complex multidimensional process, that is why it should be researched through full developed casual models. There is a need of a general model of family violence and a large base of knowledge of each type of violence. We consider that family violence should be researched through R.J. Gelles's the exchange/social theory, with F.I. Nye explanation of external and internal social control. We intend to investigate this phenomenon in Arab Sector of Israel from different perspectives.

Keywords: violence, relationship, family, conflicts, wife, husband, kids, friends, colleagues, school.

Historically, many countries and nations are considered to be violent ones. The use of Violence (VL) to obtain legitimate ends has been endorsed or at least tolerated through most the history. Movies and novels promote the concept that the use of VL to defeat, to control, to prevent and to rescue is an honorable way to proceed. Many contemporary movies hold to this pattern, where main characters are spreading mayhem and VL as they fight for right and for the good way of life. The acceptability of VL in the domestic context comes from early times.

The men are seen as being the right person to take responsibility for their women and children.

With this responsibility the men were given the power. The men, historically, have had the power to use force to control the behavior of their dependents and were expected to use so-called reasonable force in the exercise of their responsibilities. In time, the reasonable force has included beating, deprivation of food and other resources, and even the death [13].

Some reform movements were present in the Middle Age, but the unwillingness of the society to intervene in family affairs remained strong until quite recently. The use of physical force in domestic settings has been broadly publicized, that is why the public concern about the extent and

severity of the problem has been increased. The researchers suggested that the acceptance of VL in the domestic concept should decline [4]. In the same time the researchers suppose that the acceptance of VL was all the time low [*ibidem*]. The problem is that there is a need to broke the general unwillingness to allow social institutions to intervene in domestic problems.

The social activist show many dramatic cases of Domestic Violence (DV) that is why the contemporary attention and interest in this phenomenon has been increased. It is also possible to suppose, that is some cases the situation where shown with a goal to distort reality in order to win support. And this is good, because the contemporary move to criminalize DV and to provide resources for women and children who are abused is presently enjoying considerable success in changing laws and in persuading agencies to allocate additional resources for the amelioration of this social problem.

Domestic Abuse (DA) has tended to be classified in terms of type of victim or target of the Abuse (AB). When the information about abused wife was pulled out there were started many movements defending the children rights [5; 7; 8; 12]. More recently, public attention has been directed toward the plight of the elderly [13].

Spouse AB takes many shapes. A lot of public attention has been given to wife beating, with limited attention on sexual AB [9; 10; 11; 14]. Women can be abused in a number of ways [18; 19]. The revised definition of an AB includes behaviors that harm the target, then neglect, psychological and emotional AB, and sexual AB. The extent and nature of these forms of AB have not been a focus of concern and generally have not been estimated or examined other than collateral issues in cases of severe physical AB. It is also possible for a man to be targets of all these forms of AB in the domestic environment [20].

It is important to continue to research the nature and the extent of this phenomenon. The same situation is with child AB. There are researches that examined the use of physical force and the use of children for the sexual gratification of the adults. It is interesting that researchers explain the VL from two perspectives. If the focus is on causes of the behavior, it is possible that these two behaviors are completely different. One is an AB, another is a manifestation of a psychological

disturbance that produces harm to the child. If the focus is on impact of the behavior, it is possible that both of them are aspects of a common form of behavior – AB [7; 8; 12].

In case of children, there is still present an idea that it can be used in term of discipline. As so, it is tolerated. Children, as well as adults, can be harmed by neglecting or by using of psychologically damaging behaviors. An elderly abuse is a new emergent field. It means the use of abusive force. These day are mostly researched three forms of elderly AB: neglect, psychological AB, financial AB [7; 8; 12].

The researchers are still convinced that domestic AB has unclear configuration. M.A. Straus, R.J. Gelles, S.K. Steinmetz in their researches are focused on to the more visible forms of AB with focus on the harm to victims and to the victim's perspective of the AB situation [17; 18; 19; 20; 21; 22].

Generally speaking, there is also a very unclear situation about defining the nature of VL and AB. All of them, usually, point the behavior considered to be deviant. The terms AB and VL are treated as:

- physically striking and causing injury [8];
- act of striking a person with the intention to cause harm of injury but, not causing it [6; 19; 20; 21; 22];
- acts without any actual hitting, as is verbal AB, psychological or emotional VL.

And because there are a lot of definitions, there is a lack of comparability of all investigations of Family Violence (FV). A research about hitting a child is not possible to compare with a study of sexual, psychological, emotional, physical exploitation of children. Many researchers are investigating just one aspect of FV: child AB, wife AB, husband or parent AB. The most difficult methodological aspect of the process of investigation of FV is to select an adequate sample of AB and violent family to study. It is extremely difficult for a family to be interviewed in term of an AB or VL.

The AB come on surface when a child, a wife, a family member enters a hospital or protective service agencies. The FV researches still suffer from the inadequate operationalization of the dependent variables and non-representative sampling of subjects. We have the information about vulnerable families, but we still are not sure about

factors that are causing FV. There are just few investigations of FV that conceptualize the problem between family members at the family level of analysis [6].

We came to the conclusion that the lack of comparability means that there should be a large base of knowledge of one type of VL. Unfortunately, it has not been developed yet. In the same time, there is a need of a general model of FV.

The contemporary researchers speak about three broad groups of variables: individual, situational, societal. Fagan, Stewart, and Hansen speak about a general predisposition to VL, give a situational explanation of FV and speak about the role of stressful situation as a cause of FV [4].

Leonore Edna Walker speaks about VL from wife perspective. In this way the researched speaks about „learned helplessness.” [24; 25; 26].

In the same time, Walker, came to the conclusion that the interaction between husband and wife, in case of FV, has a cyclical pattern, pending between hostility and love [24; 25; 26]. Some researchers are criticizing the previous theory and insist that learned helplessness is more a response to victimization, that is a cause. In the same time, these researchers think that FV is inherently sexist. As an argument, that bring the statistical data of that time, showing that FV (wife-beating) is greater when the wife has a more prestigious job than husband.

Berkowitz tried to link the tradition of laboratory research and the aggression, in general, and FV, in particular. The researcher came to the conclusion that the aggression, in general, has one goal – to hurt another person [1; 2; 3].

The researchers came to the conclusion that because the family has an unique and very special shape, there is a need of a special theory to explain the VL in home, because contemporary theories on aggression and VL are not able to give an explanation of how family influences, impinges on, or enhances the factors that cause pain and hurt to other people [14; 17; 18].

The problem of FV was begun to be researched from scientific point of view at the end of 1960s. As one of first books about battered women is considered to be the book „Scream Quietly or the neighbors will hear” by Erin Pizzey [10; 11].

That was the first scientific voice that spoke about the problem. In the next three years the number of researches and published materials

considerably increased. Social scientists put first, very important question – how common is the phenomenon of FV in our society, because it can not be considered a social problem if it does not have incidence on millions. The second very important question was – what are the causes, why people are violent toward family members? Social scientists found, as an answer to these questions, factors related to FV. But those are not considered to be a clear knowledge and a scientific insight into the causes of FV [9].

The intra-individual level of analysis (psychopathology) tried to explain the phenomenon of FV as something that belongs to a psychologically deranged person. The clinicians encounter the cases of FV to those who are psychologically ill. The offenders have psychological problems. But, in time, the continued researches and administration of psychological tests showed that the proportion of individuals who batter their family members and suffer from psychological disorders is no bigger than the proportion of the population in general with psychological disorders [17].

In the same time, there were voices that spoke that FV is caused by the victims. The professional sources show that VL arises out of psychological problems of the victims. If a battered woman behaves strangely, it is sooner a consequence, not a cause [14]. Another theory speaks about the determining effects of learning and stress. Researchers Steele, Pollock, Bennie, Sclare investigated child abuse and found that the adult abuser were abused when been kids. Those abuses caused personality disorder that predisposed those kids, future adults, to a life pattern of VL and AB [15; 16].

More contemporary interpretations of these investigatory results tell that the experience and exposing to VL serves as a learning experience which teaches that VL can and should be used toward family members. It means, as opposition, that person that never experiences VL, will be never violent. But this is not the case. The deterministic relation experience of AB being a child and further VL in adulthood can be considered only under certain conditions [12].

Skolnick and Skolnick, develop this idea and tell that FV is a result of psychological tensions in a family and external stresses that affect all families on all social levels [23].

But, if there is a real connection between stress and VL, it means we can fail in a simplistic deterministic explanation of FV. These factors are necessary but not sufficient in explaining FV. Relations between stress and FV, is considered to be a part of a great casual flow of events that cause FV, but there are demonstrated only in an association.

Theories explaining FV are very different, from intra-psychic models to macro-sociological ones. On socio-cultural level, the explanation of FV finds relationships between income and FV, race and FV, minority status and FV [18].

From this perspective, FV is not generated by psychological disorder or social learning, but by oppressive sexism, racism and patriarchal social organization of societies. Unfortunately, the explanation of relation between income and FV, or racism/sexism and FV is very large and is not fully supported by strong empirical evidences.

One of the multi-casual model of child AB was the theory of Gil, who spoke about VL and children as a product of complex multidimensional process [7].

Unfortunately, there are still many uni-level, uni-casual, simplistic theories about FV. Full developed casual models are still rare in scientific literature and many of them are researching only child AB: Garbarino ecological model, Justice and Justice symbiosis model [5].

Fortunately, the investigations of researcher Strauss permitted to create a general system model of FV, that tries to explain all forms of FV [19; 20; 21; 22].

The exchange/social theory of researcher Richard J. Gelles, integrates the key elements of the diverse theories used to explain human VL [6].

It provides a suitable perspective to explain and answer a variety of questions concerning FV. The main idea of Gelles's theory is that human interaction is guided by the pursuit of rewards and the avoidance of punishments any costs. A person who supplies the reward to another obliges him to fulfill and obligation, in the same time, the second person must furnish benefits to the first person. If this exchange is reciprocal, the relationship will continue. If it is not reciprocal, the interaction is broken. But, sometimes a relationship is not possible to broke, even the interaction and reciprocity are stopped.

In this case increases the level of anger, resentment, conflicts and VL. The main idea of the ex-

change/social theory is – a person hit or abuse another family member because they can: 1) a person uses the VL in the family if the costs of being violent do not outweigh the rewards; 2) FV begins when social control is absent that bonds people to the social order and negatively sanction family members for acts of VL. A pregnant woman is in a great risk to be physically abused, simply because of helplessness and inability to hit back [6].

We think that family is a quiet, peaceful, loving social institution. The researcher Strauss tells that the family probably, is the most violent social institution [17; 18; 19; 20; 21; 22]. The main question is – social control is exerted to maintain a certain level of VL in families, or whether social control is designed to keep VL from occurring. From exchange/social theory point of view the social control is supposed to be an effort to prevent intra-familial VL. In the same time, the sexual and generational inequality in the families can be considered a base for reducing the chances for victims of FV to prevent or stop it. Those who are stronger, bigger, with higher status and earn more money tend to become abusers. Typically, those are husbands. Mothers apply VL on their children because the last can not respond. But, the level of VL, will minimize, while the kid raises up and become bigger and larger. Women and children, are usually, the victims, because they do not have a place and do not have enough resources to run.

The researcher Nye applied the exchange/social theory and came to the conclusion that “family VL is more common when nonnuclear family members (e. g., friends, relatives, bystanders) are unavailable, unable, or unwilling to be part of the daily system of family interaction, and thus unable to serve as agents of formal and informal social control.” [9]. There is a need to increase the degree of social control exerted over family relations and to raise the costs of intra-familial VL [*ibidem*].

From exchange/social control theory point of view, there is a great need to reduce the social isolation experienced by violent families. Violent families are more isolated than nonviolent families, that is why the possibility of external social control is reduces. Families with AB must have a greater linkages with community where they can ask and can find help or assistance in meeting stress and reducing conflicts [6].

FV appears in families where one person (husband, wife) has the complete power and makes all

the decisions. In this case, is important to share the process of decision making, to change the power structure, and to reduce the inequity in decision making. These steps can reduce the risk of conflicts and confrontation that, in many cases, goes into AB and VL.

We came to the conclusion that:

- the concept of FV has unclear configuration;
- theories explaining FV are very different, many of them being uni-level, uni-casual, and simplistic, that is why there is a lack of comparability of all investigations of FV;
- FV is considered to be a very complex multidimensional process, that is why it should be researched through full developed casual models;
- there is a need of a general model of FV and a large base of knowledge of each type of VL.

In our research, we consider that FV should be researched through R.J. Gelles's the exchange/so-

cial theory, with F.I. Nye explanation of external and internal social control. We intend to investigate this phenomenon in Arab Sector of Israel from different perspectives: realization of people cultural needs, realization of their spiritual/religious needs, the possibility of their self-development, their relationships with their personal families they come from, relationship with the families they have now, relationships with their wife/husbands, perception of VL according age, education, family status, living environment, working condition, income, living conditions, financial situation, meal, satisfaction of actual financial and material conditions, level of education, professional instructions and professional career, opinion about another gender, relationships with others, another ethnic group, other cultures, opinions about the cultural orientation of people in contemporary Arab world, opinion about another religion, other professions, the management, social-economical environment, politics.

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